

1 **Adjunctive CDK inhibition in HER2+ breast cancer to target CNS metastasis following relapse.**

2 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
3 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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8 1. CNS metastasis occurs in 50% of patients diagnosed with a type of a breast cancer known as
9 HER2-positive (HER2+), associated with over-expression of the *ERBB2* gene.

10 2. Nearly one quarter of women diagnosed with breast cancer will be diagnosed with the HER2+
11 type of breast cancer.

12 3. CNS metastasis will inevitably follow disease recurrence (“relapse”) in patients with HER2+ breast
13 cancer.

14 4. CNS metastasis is difficult to treat and frequently results in death.

15 5. We recently demonstrated that CDK10 compensates for ERBB2 inhibition and is associated with
16 trastuzumab resistance.

17 6. Treatment failure in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is associated with progression to CNS
18 metastasis.

19 7. We recently defined the full complement of kinases and phosphatases whose expression defines
20 the HER2+ subtype tumor in humans with breast cancer, and demonstrated separately that quantitative
21 determination of differential expression was sufficient for identification of synthetic lethality and kinase
22 addiction.

23 8. We demonstrated from study of RNA-sequencing measurement of total transcription following
24 pharmacologic inhibition of ERBB2 with two separate HER2 kinase inhibitors in human cancer cells *in vitro*
25 that CDK10 is compensatorily up-regulated in response to ERBB2 inhibition.

26 9. Accordingly, CDK10 induction was observed *in vivo* in HER2+ breast cancer patients who failed
27 treatment with trastuzumab (resistance).

28 10. Thus, CDK10 compensated for ERBB2 inhibition.

11. We then argued CDK10 adjunctive inhibition was a viable option for reversal or prevention of
resistance to trastuzumab.

12. We present here a Compassionate Use Protocol request for administration of a small molecule
CDK10 inhibitor in conjunction with a CDK4/6 inhibitor and trastuzumab in patients who have failed
treatment with trastuzumab

a. primary treatment failure

b. relapse following partial (PR) or complete response (CR) to trastuzumab.

13. Supporting and relevant data follow here:

14. We studied total transcription in human cancer cells treated with small molecule inhibitors of the kinase encoded by *ERBB2*, HER2, to identify kinases activated by the cancer cell to compensate for HER2 kinase inhibition.

Figure 1: Treatment of prostate cancer cells with the first generation HER2 inhibitor lapatinib results in compensatory induction of CDK10.

GSE199800

n=6 DU145 (control: *n*=3 untreated and *n*=3 DMSO treated)
n=2 DU145 treated with lapatinib

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8558	0.08537697	0.203	-1.7203052	-0.3493253	306.19	CDK10	498/11449	95.7

Figure 2: Treatment of breast cancer cells with the second generation HER2 inhibitor neratinib results in compensatory induction of CDK10.

GSE249573

n=4 MDA-MB-453 and HCC1954 (*n*=2 each; control; DMSO treated)
n=4 MDA-MB-453 and HCC1954 (*n*=2 each; control; neratinib treated)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8558	3.04E-03	0.0548	-2.9633915	-0.1624729	2008.4	CDK10	503/19129	97.4

15. Pharmacologic inhibition of the HER2 kinase in cancer cells resulted in induction of CDK10 (Figure 1 and 2). Next, we measured total transcription *in vivo* in HER2+ breast cancer patients who had developed resistance to treatment with the HER2+ monoclonal antibody trastuzumab (Figure 3).

Figure 3: CDK10 is transcriptionally activated *in vivo* in HER2+ patients who have developed resistance to trastuzumab.

GSE162187

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab; treatment sensitive
n=4 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab; treatment resistant

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8558	4.88E-02	0.583	-1.9705226	-1.1495699	929.14	CDK10	1202/19507	93.8

GSE20194

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab (pCR)
n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab with residual disease (RD)

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203469_s_at	0.00068315	-5.0648812	-0.01304	-2.4612	CDK10	135/22283	99.4

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2 16. Thus we demonstrated through measurement of total transcription in cancer cells treated with
3 small molecule inhibitors of the HER2 kinase lapatinib and neratinib that CDK10 is compensatorily
4 activated in response to HER2 inhibition.

5 17. Consistent with CDK10 activation in response to pharmacologic inhibition of HER2, we found
6 CDK10 transcriptional induction in the tumors of patients with HER2+ breast cancer that had developed
7 resistance to the HER2-targeted monoclonal antibody trastuzumab.

8 18. Co-administration of a CDK10 inhibitor with senescence-inducing CDK4/6 inhibitors (manuscript in
9 preparation) that target senescence-associated *CDKN* expression as a general mechanism by which
10 cancer cells resist treatment with chemotherapy (manuscript in preparation) is a viable strategy to
11 counteract resistance to trastuzumab.

12 19. Most CDK9 inhibitors developed have demonstrated CDK10 inhibitory potential.

13 20. Alvociclib (flavopiridol) has selective CDK10 inhibitor activity.

14 21. Other agents with CDK10 activity include:

- 15 a. NU2058
- 16 b. P276-00
- 17 c. Dinaciclib
- 18 d. SNS-032
- 19 e. AZD4573
- 20 f. AT7519
- 21 g. Riviciclib
- 22 h. NVP-2

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Citations

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2. Iorns, E., Turner, N.C., Elliott, R., Syed, N., Garrone, O., Gasco, M., Tutt, A.N., Crook, T., Lord, C.J. and Ashworth, A., 2008. Identification of CDK10 as an important determinant of resistance to endocrine therapy for breast cancer. *Cancer cell*, 13(2), pp.91-104.